

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Dounda**FIRST NAME:** Tahirou**PROGRAM CODE:** DCTD**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Professor Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied x US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did x did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did x did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is **0%**

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8) **Yes**

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. According to the coursepack, what is the first recommended step in writing an academic essay?
 - Conducting a thorough editing.
 - Drafting a conclusion.
 - Writing an introduction.
 - Starting research early.¹**

2. Which of the answers below best describes plagiarism?
 - Using another person's work without giving credit to the author.²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024) 7.

² Ibid., 34.

- Use your ideas without making citations.
 - Using statistics and data.
 - All the answers above.
3. According to the Turabian's guide, what are the two research problems?
- Empirical and theoretical.
 - Applied and practical.
 - Conceptual and practical.**³
 - Conceptual and applied.
4. Which of the following components is essential to the method chapter in quantitative research?
- Treatment.**⁴
 - Personal reflection.
 - Bibliography.
 - Social significance.
5. Based on Sampson's reflections, which of the factors below contributes mainly to the success of a research dissertation?

³ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 29.

⁴ James P. Simpson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 44.

- Collaboration between researchers and committee members.**⁵
- Avoiding critical thinking.
- Following your instincts rather than other authors' contributions
- A deep literature review.
6. In a dissertation process, what is the purpose of reflexive questions?
- To confirm research hypotheses.
- To avoid contradictory thinking.
- To ensure correct data analysis.
- To prompt critical thinking.**⁶
7. What is the correct in-text format for titles of articles within books or journals, according to the European Commission?
- Enclosed in quotation marks with only the first word capitalized unless it is a proper noun.**⁷
- Italicized with initial letters in bold on each word
- Italicized and enclosed in quotation marks.
- Italicized in parenthetical form.

⁵ James P. Simpson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 10.

⁶Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation. A Road Map from the Beginning to the End* (Los Angeles: Sage, 2019), 42.

⁷ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission* (European Union, 2021), 14.

8. Select from the list below the document that is not a component of dissertation research.

- Dissertation manuscript.
- Dissertation proposal.**⁸
- Dissertation prospectus.
- Dissertation concept paper.

9. How are compound words formed in the European Commission style?

- Hyphenated in informal texts.
- As two words without hyphens
- Follow the form in Oxford's English dictionary with hyphens used for clarity.**⁹
- Follow the form in Oxford's English dictionary with hyphens used to link.

10. Which type of analysis is most appropriate for qualitative data?

- Content analysis.
- Comparative analysis
- Statistical analysis.
- Coding and categorization.**¹⁰

⁸ James P. Simpson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 10.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 21.

¹⁰ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation. A Road Map from the Beginning to the End*, 540.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation. A Road Map from the Beginning to the End*. Los Angeles: Sage, 2019.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024.

European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. European Union, 2021.

Simpson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Tallahassee: University of Florida, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.